

Improving Informed Consent for Epidural Anesthesia to Include Post-Dural Puncture Headache Education

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Background

- Certified registered nurse anesthetists (CRNAs) are ethically responsible for obtaining informed consent for all procedures.
- Parturients are a unique challenge to obtaining informed consent due to the labor process and its environment.
- Lack of standardization for obtaining informed consent from this population can lead to unintentional omission of explaining the risks of the procedure, including post-dural puncture headache.

Purpose Statement

- The purpose of this DNP Project was to develop an education module for CRNAs at Kaiser Permanente San Bernardino County to improve the informed consent process for parturients and meet professional practice standards, including education on possible dural punctures and their sequelae.

Review of Literature

- Barriers to informed consent include parturients' labor pain and rushed anesthesia providers due to urgent nature of caring for parturients (Wilson and Burkle, 2020).
- Incomplete informed consent leads to lack of patient knowledge on PDPH (Bashir et al., 2021).
- Delayed treatment of PDPH leads to subdural hematoma, postpartum depression, and decreased maternal breastfeeding (Vallejo & Zakowski, 2022).
- Standardization improves obtaining thorough consent in any circumstance (Clarke et al., 2018).

Methods

- Design: The design of this study was a pre-post intervention evaluation study.
- Participants and setting: 15 obstetrical (OB) CRNAs at Kaiser San Bernardino County from September 6, 2023 to November 19, 2023.
- Instrument: The instrument used for this project was an 8-item informed consent abstraction tool and suggested scoring approach published by the British Journal of Medicine with a Spearman's coefficient of 0.91 to establish construct validity.
- Intervention: The intervention was a 15-minute informed consent education module.
- The Iowa Model was the framework that guided this project (Buckwater et al., 2017).

Domain	Item	Response	Points
Description of procedure			
Content/presentation	1. Is language describing what the procedure is (beyond the medical name) provided for the patient? (plain language)	'Yes' 'No'	2 0
Presentation	1a. If provided, is it typed?	'Yes' 'No' 'N/A'	1 0 0
Content/presentation	2. Is a description of how the procedure will be performed provided for the patient? (plain language)	'Yes' 'No'	2 0
Presentation	2a. If provided, is it typed?	'Yes' 'No' 'N/A'	1 0 0
Rationale for procedure			
Content	3. Is the clinical rationale (condition-specific justification) for why the procedure will be performed provided?	'Yes, context and condition given and fully meet criteria' 'Context and condition given, but do not fully meet criteria' 'No, no rationale given'	2 1 0
Patient-oriented benefits			
Content	4. Is any patient-oriented benefit provided (intended impact on the patient's health, longevity and/or quality of life)?	'Yes' 'No'	2 0
Probability of procedure-specific risks			
Content	5. Is a quantitative probability provided for any procedure-specific risk?	'Yes' 'No'	2 0
Content	6. Is a qualitative probability provided for any procedure-specific risk?	'Yes' 'No'	1 0
Alternative(s) to the procedure			
Content	7. Is any alternative provided for the patient?	'Yes' 'No'	2 0
Timing			
Timing	8a. Date the document was shared with the patient; if not available, the patient's/proxy's date of signature.	At least 1 day before procedure OR patient opted out of viewing the informed consent document at least 1 day prior.	5
Timing	8b. Date of procedure.	Less than 1 day before procedure.	0
Timing	8c. Patient opted out of receiving the consent document at least 1 day prior to the procedure.	Missing either date of patient's/proxy's signature or missing date of procedure.	0
Maximum quality score			
			20

For item 3, either 0, 1 or 2 points are granted. N/A, not applicable.

Strengths and Limitations

- The results were statistically significant showing importance of standardization
- The time gaps between completing the education module and post-intervention audit was inconsistent
- Principal investigator completed data collection creating possible bias

Discussion

- Epidural informed consent is easily interrupted, leading to omission of key components
- Standardizing this process improves quality of informed consent and its components
- Thorough epidural informed consent leads to increased patient education and improves patient outcomes for PDPH and other epidural procedure risks

Recommendations

- Standardization of informed consent processes improved the quality of informed consent, increasing patient education on post-dural puncture headaches and improving patient outcomes

Results

Graph 1. Changes in Informed Consent Audit Scores

Graph 2. Correlation of years worked as CRNA and Pre-intervention Scores

- The mean preintervention informed consent audit score was 5.40 (SD ± 2.32) out of 20 and the postintervention informed consent audit score's mean was 9.40 (SD ± 2.35).
- The difference between pre- and post-education module scores was statistically significant (p<0.001).
- There was no correlation between the participant's demographic data and their pre or post-intervention scores, including how many years worked as a CRNA.
- There are no correlation between any of the demographic variables and scores.

References

